

Chemical imprints in atmospheric abundances of stars with massive planets

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Abstract

Stellar parameters of 25 stars with detected massive planets and abundances of 25 elements from Li to Eu were investigated based on homogeneous high resolution spectra. The abundance of iron [Fe/H] and key elements (Li, C, O, Mg and Si), indicative of the planet formation, as well as the dependencies of [El/Fe] on the condensation temperature (T_{cond}), were analyzed. We found some interesting results: the mean values of C/O and [C/O] are $\langle C/O \rangle = 0.48 \pm 0.07$ and $\langle [C/O] \rangle = -0.07 \pm 0.07$, they are slightly lower than the solar ones; the Mg/Si ratios range from 0.83 to 0.95 for four stars in our sample and from 1.0 to 1.86 for the remaining 21 stars; there are various slopes of [El/Fe] versus T_{cond} . The dependencies of the planetary mass on metallicity, Li abundance, C/O and Mg/Si ratios and also on the [El/Fe]- T_{cond} slopes were examined.

1 Introduction

Investigation of the chemical composition of planet host stars and its connection with their possessing planets is an important component of the study of stars with planetary systems. The main features of the chemical composition of parent stars, reckoned as possible indicators of the presence of planets, are follows: 1) Metallicity, [Fe/H] (Gonzalez, 1997; Sousa *et al.*, 2008); 2) Lithium abundance, $\log A(\text{Li})$ (Israelian *et al.*, 2004; Gonzalez *et al.*, 2010; Delgado Mena *et al.*, 2015; Figueira *et al.*, 2014); 3) Carbon and oxygen abundances, as well as their ratios, C/O, [C/O] (Delgado Mena *et al.*, 2010; Nissen *et al.*, 2014); 4) Magnesium-to-silicon abundances ratios, Mg/Si, [Mg/Si] (Adibekyan *et al.*, 2015); and 5) The ratio of volatile to refractory elements and their dependence on the condensation temperature T_{cond} (Udry & Santos, 2007; Meléndez *et al.*, 2009). In this study, we present an analysis of the abundances of the above-listed elements for 25 stars with massive planets.

2 Observations, stellar parameters, chemical composition

The studied stars were selected from the SOPHIE Exoplanet Consortium programmes (Bouchy *et al.*, 2009). We used spectra adopted from the archive of the SOPHIE echelle spectrograph (Perruchot *et al.*, 2011) on the 1.93m telescope of OHP (France), a resolving power of $R \sim 75,000$ and the wavelengths range restricted to 4400–6800 Å (Moultaka *et al.*, 2004).

The atmospheric parameters were derived as follows: the effective temperature, T_{eff} upon independence of the iron abundance, $\log A(\text{Fe})$, on the lower level excitation potential, E_{low} ; the gravity, $\log g$ – through the iron ionisation balance; the microturbulent velocity, V_t , based on the independence of the iron abundance, $\log A(\text{Fe})$, determined from

the equivalent width, EW, of Fe I lines, from EW of given line.

Elemental abundances were determined under LTE approximations using stellar atmosphere models by Castelli & Kurucz (2004). We employed the WIDTH9 code by R. Kurucz for the abundance determination from EW of lines, and also a new version of the LTE STARSP software package by Tsymbal (1996) for spectral synthesis using the latest VALD atomic data from Kupka *et al.* (1999). Hyperfine structure (HFS) was factored in for Sc, V, Mn, Ba and Eu.

3 Results

To highlight the possible connections between indicators and the presence of planets, we examined the relationship between the chemical composition and different parameters, including the mass of the planet, M_{pl} , expressed in Jupiter mass units M_J . The dependencies of [Fe/H] vs. T_{eff} and M_{pl} vs. [Fe/H] are presented in Fig. 1, while those of the Li abundances vs. T_{eff} , vsini and M_{pl} are depicted in Fig. 2; [C/O] vs. [Fe/H], C/O vs. [Fe/H] and M_{pl} illustrated in Fig. 3; [Mg/Si] vs. [Fe/H] (with the data for disc stars added from Mishenina *et al.* (2016)), Mg/Si vs. [Fe/H] and M_{pl} are shown in Fig. 4.

The following has been discovered for our target stars: 1) There are some stars with a [Fe/H] lower than the solar one (see Fig. 1), and there is also a correlation between the planet's mass and metallicity that arises from a number of factors (Adibekyan, 2019); 2) The lithium abundance reflects the evolution of lithium with age, the dependence of lithium on the rotation velocity, vsini, as well as a weak dependence on the mass of the planet (see Fig. 2); 3) There is a slight deficiency (-0.07) of the average [C/O] ratio, and no dependence of C/O on the mass of the planet (see Fig. 3); 4) The trend of Mg/Si vs. [Fe/H] reflects the Galactic Chemical Evolution, in the meantime, the Mg/Si ratio shows a slightly negative trend with the mass of the planet (see Fig. 4); 5) There is a

 Figure 1: $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ vs. T_{eff} and M_{pl} vs. $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

negative trend of the slopes, which represent the correlation between elemental abundances and condensation temperature for a given star with the mass of the planet.

4 Conclusions

Our new and independent study of 25 stars with massive planets has yielded the following features of the chemical composition:

- The stars in our sample do not exhibit high carbon-to-oxygen ratios (C/O ratios do not exceed 0.8);
- The Mg/Si ratio for most (80%) stars is in the range from 1.0 to 1.86;
- For the lithium abundance, as well as for C/O, [C/O] ratios, no dependence on the planetary mass has been detected with a slope greater than the error value, while some correlation between the planetary mass and either metallicity or the Mg/Si ratio has been observed; and
- For most of the studied stars, the trends of the abundances of refractory and volatile elements versus T_{cond} cannot be identified clearly and distinctly; besides, the absolute values of the slopes are smaller than the errors.

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 Figure 2: Li vs. T_{eff} , $vsini$ and M_{pl} .

Figure 3: $[C/O]$ vs. $[Fe/H]$, C/O vs. $[Fe/H]$ and M_{pl} .

Figure 4: $[Mg/Si]$ vs. $[Fe/H]$ (with the data for disc stars, marked by points), Mg/Si vs. $[Fe/H]$ and M_{pl} .

Figure 5: Dependence of the $\Delta[\text{El}/\text{Fe}]-T_{\text{cond}}$ slope on the planetary mass M_{pl} .

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